

Public Relations Relation of İstanbul and Venice

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Abstract

Istanbul; Byzantine period; surrounded by walls, Constantinople period; the Istanbul period, which gained political importance; Venice, which became a part of Italy in 1866, has experienced many changes and developments in the political, cultural and social fields. The correlation of public relations in both cities is quite high.

Keywords: Public Relations, Relation of Istanbul and Venice, Istanbul and Venice

Limitedness

The limitations of the research are limited to the scope of the subject in the light of world literature and data. The research was limited to closely related author and literature topics. Restricted by literature review.

Notifications

Evaluation: Evaluated by internal and external consultants.

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Ethical Statement

Publication ethics of the relevant regulations of our university; It is a national-based scientific study that aims to ensure that scientific research and publications are carried out in accordance with basic principles such as honesty, openness, objectivity, and respect for the findings and creations of others, and works for the realization of these principles in the field of related sciences.

Picture 1: Satellite Image of Istanbul

Source: <https://www.cnnturk.com/dunya/istanbulun-uydu-goruntuleriyle-32-yillik-degisimi?page=1> Date of access: 20.07.2023

The conquest of Istanbul by the Ottoman Empire was its biggest project. This project of the empire led to the construction of all other projects (Alkan, 2014). In the eyes of travelers, Istanbul, which was a magnificent, rich, Christian religion and intense commercial center during the Byzantine period, is a matter of understanding and is not only the center of Turkey but also the center of the East.

Source: <https://www.google.com/maps/place/Venedik,+%C4%B0talya/@45.4045432,12.3873328,32646m/data=!3m2!1e3!4b1!4m6!3m5!1s0x477eb1daf1d63d89:0x7ba3c6f0bd92102f18m2!3d45.4408474!4d12.3155151!16zL20vMDdfcGY?entry=ttu> Date of access: 20.07.2023

Venice, built on 118 islands connected by bridges and separated by canals in northeastern Italy, and between the deltas of the Piave and Po rivers, means 'Venezia' in Italian and Venetian; It means 'Venexia'. Famous for its works of art, natural beauty and architecture, Venice, including the abalone, is on the list of World Heritage Sites (<https://tr.wikipedia.org/wiki/Venice> Access Date: 20.07.2023). This study will seek answers to the following questions:

1. What is the Public Relations relation of Istanbul?
2. What is Venice's PR correlation?
3. What is the Public Relations relation of Istanbul and Venice?

Having hosted many civilizations in history, Istanbul is still a rare metropolitan city today. Venice, which is not only a center of trade, is also known as the city of lovers. These two cities cross paths in terms of being trade centers. Both cultural heritage and works of art etc. reveals its features related to public relations.

from the literature

Istanbul, where east and west meet, is located at the crossroads of its continent. It was the Bosphorus that divided Asia and Europe, the Sea of Marmara and the Black Sea, the Golden Horn (Ziyalan and Spangler, 2008). Floating in the ocean, with slang or nautical displays like townspeople or sea magnates, Venice (Evans, Foster and Rogers, 1860) would travel with small traders.

Picture 3: Ducal Palace (Palazzo Ducale))

Source: <https://ozhanozturk.com/2019/04/06/duk-sarayi-palazzo-ducale-venedik/> Date of access: 20.07.2023

The Doge's Palace, built in a Gothic style and used by the duchies of Venice, was used as a political center for the Republic of Venice. It also hosted political institutions until the invasion of Napoleon. Today, this palace was built between 1309-1424 and was built on a tiny castle. Dolmabahçe Palace, which takes its name from here due to its soil structure and filling, 17th century such as İstinye, Büyükdere and Tarabya. It has the feature of being an inland bay. This place was filled during the reigns of Osman II and Ahmet I (Gülersoy, 1984).

Picture 4: Dolmabahçe Palace

Source: https://tr.wikipedia.org/wiki/Dolmabah%C3%A7e_Saray%C4%B1 Date of access: 20.07.2023

The spiral technique was used in this study. The universe of the research is limited to Istanbul and Venice. In the study, the two-sided closed technique was used. The research was also guided by the double helix method. Two paired helices on the same axis are called 'double helix' and they are the translation of one to the other (<https://tr.wikipedia.org/wiki/Helix> Access Date: 20.07.2023).

Argument

Being at a point that connects the Asian and European continents, Istanbul provides the passage between 2 continents with its Bosphorus and has many economic contributions to Turkey. Istanbul, which is considered to be very important politically; It is a way between the Far East and Europe and supports countries to communicate. Health, education, etc. It also has great opportunities in terms of (Tuna, 2015). World history, location, socio-cultural life and economy are in a very important position. As it is known, Istanbul is the only city in the world founded on 3 continents. It was an important force in the seas in the Middle Ages and the Renaissance period, 13th century - 17th century. In the Republic of Venice, which was the center of trade and art until the end of the year, many artistic movements took their place, especially in the Renaissance Period. Venice played an important role in the development of opera and symphonic music and is the city where Antonio Vivaldi was born.

Research Strategy

The church of San Polo, known as San Zanipolo, is one of the largest churches in Venice with minor basilica status. This house of worship with Italian Gothic architectural style is one of the Dominican denomination churches in Venice and was built for preaching to crowded congregations (https://tr.wikipedia.org/wiki/Santi_Giovanni_ve_Paolo_Church Access Date: 20.07.2023). Hürrem Sultan Tomb, whose tomb frame is made of verse and door metal tiles, is filled with stalactite niches between the windows and is decorated with plum and tulip flowers. Hürrem Sultan and III. Selim's son, Sultan Mehmet, and Ahmet II's daughter, Hatice Sultan, are

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buried (Öz, 1997), As can be seen, the cities of Istanbul and Venice have taken the form of a whole with their history and religious structures. These cities, which have become frequent destinations by travelers and merchants, are called brand cities. Brand cities, on the other hand, become places where tourists visit regularly. Shrines and churches form the basis of major religions. Social areas are an indispensable part of our lives and culture.

Conclusion

Taksim Square, which hosts crowds and rallies, is a place of silence and wreath laying of official people, schools and delegations affiliated to the command of warships, is among the important points that give life to the city, and there is a monument symbolizing the Republic in this square. San Marco Square, which is the most visited square of Venice by pigeons and tourists, has a length of 175 and a width of 82 meters. Napoleon used the phrase 'Europe's most beautiful festival area' and Alfred de Musset used the phrase 'Europe's Hall'.

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